

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ОЦІНКА МОЖЛИВОСТЕЙ МЕТАЛОШУКАЧІВ ТА РАДІОТЕХНІЧНОЇ СИСТЕМИ ІДЕНТИФІКАЦІЇ МЕТАЛІВ ЯК ЗАСОБУ ЕКСПРЕС КОНТРОЛЮ

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EVALUATION OF THE POSSIBILITIES OF METAL DETECTORS AND THE RADIO ENGINEERING SYSTEM OF IDENTIFICATION OF METALS AS A MEANS OF EXPRESS CONTROL

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АНОТАЦІЯ

Наводяться результати досліджень ідентифікації металів металодетектором професійного класу Minelab equinox 800 та вихростумової радіотехнічної системи. Розглянуто особливості роботи металодетектора та радіотехнічної системи, наведено результати розрізнення магнітних та немагнітних металів. На базі срібних монет показано, що вихростумова радіотехнічна система дозволяє розрізнити між собою сплави різних металів. Результати ідентифікації срібних монет за інформаційними ознаками доповнені значенням питомої густини, показали, що різні за вмістом вторинного металу монети є різними сплавами із дуже близькими характеристиками. Показана перспектива використання системи для експрес-аналізу металів та сплавів.

ABSTRACT

The results of metal identification studies with a professional class Minelab equinox 800 metal detector and a vortex radio engineering system are given. The peculiarities of the operation of the metal detector and the radio engineering system are considered, and the results of distinguishing between magnetic and non-magnetic metals are given. On the basis of silver coins, it is shown that the eddy current radio engineering system makes it possible to distinguish between alloys of different metals. The results of the identification of silver coins based on informational features, supplemented with the value of specific density, showed that coins with different secondary metal content are different alloys with very similar characteristics. The perspective of using the system for express analysis of metals and alloys is shown.

Ключові слова: електромагнітні властивості металів, вихростумовий перетворювач, дистанційна ідентифікація металів, металодетектор Minelab equinox 800, амплітудно-фазовий метод реєстрації сигналів.

Keywords: electromagnetic properties of metals, eddy current converter, remote identification of metals, Minelab equinox 800 metal detector, amplitude-phase signal registration method.

- Statement of the problem

There are a large number of different metals. These are magnetic (iron, steel, nickel, etc.) and non-magnetic materials and alloys (aluminum, copper, silver, gold, etc.). Different methods are used for their identification: chemical research, research of the object by X-ray-fluorescence methods, etc. In most cases, they require laboratory research, which requires physical damage to the surface of the object under study. Therefore, the task of distinguishing metal objects remotely and without physical damage is relevant for many branches of the economy, for example, materials science.

To detect and identify metal objects, eddy current devices (ECD) are used, which use the phenomenon of

surface currents in metal when it is irradiated by a variable electromagnetic field and have a common name - metal detectors. There is a fairly large number of types of ECD [1, 2]. They are mainly designed to detect hidden metal objects. In most cases, ECD allow only a dichotomous assessment. That is, to determine to which class (ferrous or non-ferrous metal) the investigated metal object belongs. However, identification of metals in the middle of subclasses of metals (discrimination function) is still not fully resolved. Although some of the manufacturers of metal detectors claim the ability to recognize the investigated objects by type of metal. One of these modern devices is the Minelab equinox 800 metal detector manufactured by Minelab [3, 4].

- Analysis of the latest research and publications

Recently, there have been works related to the development of new methods of discrimination of metals and eddy current devices, which allow identification of metals in the middle of subclasses of ferrous or non-ferrous metals. They are based on the measurement of the phase shift between the probing signal and the response signal obtained due to signal reradiation [5,6]. Thus, in [5], an analysis of existing methods of phase shift detection is carried out. These are two methods, the first of which is the use of a phase synchronous detector, and the second is digital processing of the response signal in order to measure and calculate the orthogonal components of the signal (active R and reactive X) and further calculate the signal phase shift $\varphi = \arctg(X/R)$. Unfortunately, this paper does not present the results of research on specific metals, but only provides a structural diagram of the device and its possible implementation.

The eddy current radio engineering system (RS), which is described in [1, 2], uses the method of measuring the phase shift with a synchronous detector and dynamic scanning of the investigated objects for the express control of metals.

- Allocation unresolved parts of the general problem

However, the evaluation of the possibilities of identification of metals and alloys by modern metal de-

tectors and the radio engineering system of identification of metals has not been carried out, the peculiarities of the use of the discrimination function by these devices in the express analysis of metal samples have not been identified.

- The purpose of the article

The purpose of the work is to analyze the possibilities of the considered devices and to determine ways to further improve the technical characteristics of identification devices built on the basis of the use of eddy current processes occurring in metal objects.

- Presenting main material

Consider the Minelab equinox 800 metal detector produced by Minelab [3, 4], which is a modern ECD and which, as the manufacturer claims, has a discrimination function.

The structural diagram of the Minelab equinox type metal detector is shown in Fig. 1 [7].

The digital unit (1) forms sinusoidal signals by two DACs (2,3). The generated signals can be quadrature (phase shift of 90 degrees) or have a different phase shift between them. The frequency of the signals can vary in the range of 1kHz - 100kHz. Amplified signals (4) through the matching unit (5) are fed to the transmission coil (6), which has several resonant frequencies. The current through the coil of the antenna and the voltage on it, which are necessary for amplitude-phase correction during phase self-adjustment of the device at operating frequencies, are measured by an ADC (7,8).

Figure 1 – Block diagram of Minelab equinox series metal detectors [7]

The signal from the receiving coil (9), containing the response signal from the detected metal sample and guidance from the mineralized soil through the input amplifier (10) and the ADC (11), is fed to the input of the digital unit (1). The filtered signals are sent to the secondary processing unit (12), in which the useful signal is selected and discriminated. The audio amplifier (14) and the speaker (15) together with the display (16) transform the information into an operator-friendly form.

The ECD uses a digital IQ demodulator and a low-pass filter. Such a combination of nodes allows obtaining a better signal-to-noise ratio and is less susceptible to interference than synchronous demodulators and low-pass filters, which is usually used in a conventional analog tone (CW) metal detector [5, 6, 8]. This is because the IQ demodulator uses sinusoidal reference signals, while the reference signals for analog synchronous demodulators use pulse width signals (PWM signals). The numerous harmonics of such a signal allow

noise and interfering signals to drown out the demodulated signals. At the same time, digital low-pass filters, if properly designed, have a very steep attenuation filter characteristic outside the passband, which limits the amount of interference that affects circuit performance.

The metal detector on the screen (Fig. 2) displays an abstract number that characterizes the conductivity

of the object and by the value of which you can estimate what kind of metal it is. The digital object recognition system has gradations from -9 to 40 (Fig. 3). Only a highly qualified operator can determine the specific material based on his experience, which is a subjective assessment (Fig. 3).

Figure 2 – Indicators of the metal detector display when examining iron - a) and aluminum - b)

The gradations of the Minelab equinox display and their correspondence to the detected metal are taken from the operating instructions [3] and shown in Fig. 3.

From -9 to 0 steel	From 1 to 10 very low conductivity	from 11 to 20 low conductivity	from 21 to 30 high conductivity	from 31 to 40 very high conductivity

Figure 3 – The gradations of the Minelab equinox [3]

The eddy current radio engineering system (RS) [1] uses the measurement of the phase shift between the probing signal and the response signal with the help of a synchronous phase detector [9, 10], and due to the use of methods (spectral and graphic-digital) of signal processing embedded in it, it can more accurately identify metal. A feature of the system is the dynamic scanning

of the object under study. In addition, in order to improve the characteristics, the authors carried out modernization of the RS.

The structural diagram of the modernized RS is shown in Fig. 4 [11, 12]. The ECD consists of an antenna system (transmitting and receiving coils), a low-frequency signal generator, amplification and signal processing units, a clock generator, a microcontroller, and an indicator device.

Figure 3 – The structural diagram of the modernized RS

The low-frequency signal generator generates signals with a frequency of 6.6 kHz, which, with the help of a transmission coil, emit an electromagnetic field into the environment under study. As a result of electromagnetic induction, Foucault currents (surface currents) appear on the surface of the investigated metal object, which are registered by the receiving coil, cause a response signal in it and are fed to the amplification and primary processing unit.

Synchronization between nodes is provided by a clock pulse generator. After processing in the phase detector, the analog signal is digitized and fed to the microcontroller unit. The dynamic range of the ADC of the microcontroller is about 84 dB. In the microcontroller, the signals obtained from the tested samples are compared with the reference ones [13], which are stored in the memory of the microcontroller. The result of the comparison is sent to the indicator device. The modernized RS is built on a dual-core STM32H745 microcontroller. The first core controls the operation of the eddy current unit, the second core ensures the conversion of measured data into the format necessary for further transmission to the indicator device (laptop HP 4540s). Information is transferred to a personal computer in 16-bit packets [14,15]. A USB port is used for connection. The MATLAB application program package is installed on the RS, in the environment of which the numerical determination of classification features is

carried out with the help of the response signal amplitude normalization program and computer programs for grapho-digital imaging and spectral methods.

Dynamic scanning of a metal object is carried out by a rotary laboratory setup, which allows to stabilize the relative movement of the antenna system and the metal under study, and allows changing the relative speed of movement of objects in a plane parallel to them in the range of speeds from 2 to 8 m/s.

The research was conducted on a stand capable of recording the distance of the antenna of the eddy current device from the object. The stand consists of a base on which the antenna of one of the devices (Minelab or RS) currently used for measurements is placed, a rotary setup and a system for adjusting the distance between the antenna system and the object under study.

The results of the readings of the metal detector display when scanning various metals are summarized in the table. 1. For each metal, 20 scans were performed parallel to the plane of the coil. The antenna system lay on a chipboard, and the metal samples were moved at the level of the base of the stand (on the board of the table). The distance between the antenna system and the scanned samples was 170 mm. The scanning speed was about 0.4 m/s. Samples were studied that were made of magnetic materials (iron, cobalt, nickel), graphite and non-magnetic (rest) materials.

Table 1

Results of detection of metals by a metal detector at a frequency of 5kHz

№	Material	Target ID & Discrimination				
		1-4	5-8	9-12	13-16	17-20
1	Steel	-7. -9 -8. -7	-7. -7. -8. -8	-8. -9. -7. -8	-7. -8. -7. -8	-7. -8. -7. -8
2	Cobalt	19. 15. 18. 11	17. 8 17. 7.	17. 6. 17. 6.	17. 6. 17. 6.	17. 5. 18. 12
3	Nickel	26. 31. 26. 30.	27. 30. 27. 30.	26. 31. 25. 31	26. 30. 26. 30.	25. 31. 27. 31
4	Graphite	1. 1. 1. 2.	7. 1. 2. 1.	1. 1. 1. 1.	5. 1. 2. 1.	4. 1. 1. 1.
5	Aluminum	31. 31. 31. 30.	30. 31. 30. 30.	31. 30. 31. 31.	31. 30. 30. 31.	30. 31. 30. 31
6	Cadmium	26. 28. 27. 26.	26. 26. 27. 27.	27. 27. 27. 27.	27. 27. 27. 28.	26. 28. 26. 27.
7	Tungsten	32. 32. 32. 32.	31. 32. 31. 32.	31. 32. 32. 32.	31. 31. 31. 32.	32. 32. 31. 32.
8	Magnesium	33. 35. 35. 35.	35. 35. 35. 35.	35. 35. 35. 35.	35.35. 35. 35.	35. 35. 35. 35.
9	Lead	26. 26. 26. 26.	26. 26. 26. 26.	26. 26. 26. 26.	26. 26. 26. 26.	26. 26. 26. 26.
10	Niobium	27. 27. 27. 27.	27. 27. 28. 27.	27. 27. 27. 27.	27. 27. 27. 27.	27. 27. 28. 27.
11	Titanium	5. 8. 8. 8.	12. 12. 8. 7.	9. 7. 8. 7.	10. 9. 8. 8.	11. 10. 9. 8.
12	Molybdenum	29. 29. 30. 29.	29. 30. 30. 29.	29. 29. 29. 29.	28. 29. 29. 30.	29. 29. 29. 28.
13	Vanadium	18. 18. 18. 18.	17. 19. 18.18.	18. 17. 18.17.	18. 17. 18. 17.	18. 18. 18. 18.

As can be seen from the table. 1 different types of metals are identified by the metal detector in the same number (nickel magnetic and non-magnetic tungsten, niobium, cadmium) or (non-magnetic aluminum, molybdenum) or (cobalt magnetic and non-magnetic vanadium), which is a confirmation that the common approach of determining the type of metals in serial metal

detectors can uniquely identify them only by the magnetic/non-magnetic feature.

The results of identification of metals by the eddy current radio engineering system are given in table. 2. Samples are grouped according to the table of chemical elements (by group growth from left to right and period from top to bottom).

Table 2

Results of determination metals by RS

№ II №	Metal type or alloy	Coeffi- cient K%	Symme- try coefficient	Coeffi- cient correlations	Spec-trum area by level -80dB (dB*Hz)	Spec- trum lower limit	Spec-trum upper limit
		K%	Esym	Cor	Sxs	fn	fv
1	Carbon	47.60± 0.54	22.43± 0.42	43.99± 0.70	1410.7± 22.57	0.73± 0.01	39.55± 0.04
2	Steel	42.37± 0.62	-15.37± 0.97	45.06± 0.98	1209.8± 20.71	0.38± 0.04	31.84± 0.82
3	Cobalt	72.95± 0.92	23.84± 0.73	39.46± 0.98	1494.7± 18.21	1.24± 0.02	33.43± 0.77
4	Nickel	40.23± 0.46	29.43± 0.58	40.88± 0.65	1388.6± 21.11	1.59± 0.02	31.65± 0.62
5	Magnesium	42.03± 0.89	30.03± 0.47	42.37± 0.60	1466.0± 18.94	1.05± 0.10	36.33± 0.88
6	Aluminum	43.18± 0.73	29.53± 0.76	42.37± 0.67	1414.2± 24.75	1.28± 0.01	34.71± 0.77
7	Titanium	42.19± 0.77	21.28± 0.55	47.20± 0.58	1544.0± 21.96	0.71± 0.02	45.41± 0.66
8	Vanadium	43.31± 0.43	27.53± 0.52	40.73± 0.37	1402.5± 16.45	1.56± 0.0173	32.16± 0.02
9	Copper	46.06± 0.54	26.31± 0.34	43.08± 0.65	1398.2± 20.33	1.30± 0.01	34.51± 0.23
10	Brass	43.12± 0.24	31.33± 0.58	39.46± 0.22	1430.2± 18.43	1.16± 0.05	31.63± 0.57
11	Niobium	45.81± 0.64	32.08± 0.55	40.63± 0.94	1464.3± 22.12	1.54± 0.02	33.80± 0.61
12	Molybdenum	44.25± 0.57	31.50± 0.40	44.42± 0.95	1519.0± 22.43	1.96± 0.02	43.42± 0.91
13	Silver 9999 (1hr 2012)	46.07± 0.85	30.50± 0.57	38.68± 0.59	1414.9± 16.67	1.69± 0.18	29.79± 0.50
14	Gold 9999 (2hr 2012)	48.74± 0.96	21.23± 0.66	39.97± 0.51	1313.0± 18.51	1.31± 0.04	29.99± 0.98
15	Lead	44.28± 0.98	24.98± 0.64	42.53± 0.81	1414.9± 20.86	1.75± 0.03	40.72± 0.66

The analysis shows that the quantitative values of information signs for different metals differ from each other, which allows to identify the metal from which the object under study is made by their numerical values. Metal identification can be carried out by comparing information features for the studied metal with their

quantitative estimates for known samples (listed in Table 2). Table 3 shows the results of research on silver coins [16,17]. The table contains an additional column - density.

Results of determination of silver by RS

№ II№	Metal type or alloy	Charac- teristics dimen- sions	Coeffi- cient K%	Symme- try coeffi- cient	Coeffi- cient correla- tions	Spec- trum area by level -80dB (dB*Hz)	Spec- trum lower limit	Spec- trum upper limit
		Mass, density	K%	Esym	Cor	Sxs	fn	fv
1	900 (2 flor 1874 AuHu emp)	mas 24,71 den 10,38	45.76± 0.92	26.00± 0.52	42.19± 0.48	1391.9± 19.63	1.43± 0.03	33.62± 0.77
2	900 (1 flor 1889 AuHu emp)	mas 12,31 den 10,34	44.16± 0.82	27.65± 0.92	40.87± 0.42	1391.0± 14.13	1.72± 0.03	32.67± 0.85
3	900 (1 flor 1878 AuHu emp)	mas 12,39 den 10,24	44.63± 0.90	26.57± 0.94	41.15± 0.64	1378.1± 15.79	1.97± 0.0139	33.06± 0.62
4	900 (50 frank 1977 10% copp France)	mas 29,93 den 10,39	45.44± 0.91	29.41± 0.73	43.43± 0.50	1435.8± 21.34	1.85± 0.04	42.11± 0.50
5	900 (50 cent 1967 Kenedi USA)	mas 11,37 den 9,47	42.65± 0.66	29.23± 0.68	37.68± 0.65	1380.9± 17.45	1.92± 0.01	29.01± 0.57
6	900 (50 cent 1968 Kenedi USA)	mas 11,63 den 9,45	44.26± 0.90	28.77± 0.65	37.65± 0.63	1376.3± 14.55	2.14± 0.04	29.30± 0.45

The density was measured on a scale with a resolution of 0.01 g, which was verified by a weight of the M1 accuracy class (permissible error of 3 mg). The calculated value of the density clearly showed that for modern silver coins of the same sample the density is the same, accordingly the informative coefficients are the same.

Older coins have a significant spread of density within one cataloged sample of silver - this was discovered after measuring more than 90 different silver coins and selectively checking their chemical composition on an X-ray fluorescence analyzer. From this it can be concluded that during the stamping of coins at different times, there was no combination of silver and copper acceptable today, and different metals (copper, zinc, antimony and others) were added to the silver.

The measurements showed that silver coins are essentially different alloys with similar characteristics.

CONCLUSIONS

Let's consider the disadvantages and advantages of devices. The metal detector [18] does not allow, unlike RS, to determine what metal the object under study is made of. But it allows you to quickly detect its presence and the class of metal (colored or black) even when they are hidden. RS allows you to determine to which group a metal belongs and what kind of metal it is, but for identification it is necessary to process a large array of data, which at the current stage is done manually, by analyzing the received data by an operator. This is painstaking work that depends on the operator's qualifications and takes a lot of time when processing the received data array. For the effective use of RS, it is

necessary to automate the process of processing this array by using artificial intelligence (AI) methods, such as the support vector method [19, 20]. After these works, the eddy current radiotechnical system can be used for express analysis of alloys, while the metal detector should be used to search for hidden metal objects.

References

1. Abramovych A. O. Eddy-Current Amplitude-Phase Based Method for Identifying Conductive (Metal) Objects / A. O. Abramovych, V. O. Poddubny // "International scientific and technical journal" Metallophysics and the latest technologies". Kyiv. – 2020. – T. 42. – №. 8. – С. 1069-1085. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15407/mfint.42.08.1169>
2. Abramovych A. O. The remote eddy-current analysis of a composition of metal objects / A. O. Abramovych, I. S. Kashirsky, V. O. Piddubny // Metallophysics and advanced technologies. – 2017. – Vol.39, №8. – P. 1035-1049. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15407/mfint.39.08.1035>
3. Прилад Minelab equinox 800 / Керівництво користувача https://www.minelab.com/_files/f/327483/4901-0270-1%20Inst.%20Manual,%20EQUINOX%20600%20800%20RU.pdf
4. [Electronic resource] Retrieved from: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iTIW5L_GNZE (accessed 18 February 2024) [in English]
5. Bruschini C. A Multidisciplinary analysis of frequency domain metal detectors for humanitarian demining: thesis dissertation of Doctor in Applied

Sciences / Claudio Bruschini.– Brussels: Vrije Universiteit Brussel, 2002.– 242 p.

6. Voprosy podpoverkhnostnoy radyolokatsyy /A. Yu. Hrynev Moskva: Radyotekhnika: 2005 (in Russian).

7. Method and apparatus for metal detection employing digital signal processing United States Patent Minelab US 7432,715 B2 oct.7.2008

8. Nerazrushayushchiy kontrol'. V 5-ti knigakh. Kniga 3. Elektromagnitnyy kontrol' / V. V. Sukhorukov Moskva: Vysshaya shkola: 1992 (in Russian).

9. Kontrol' nerazrushayushchiy vikhretkovyy. Terminy i opredeleniya, (GOST 24289-80) (in Russian).

10. Nakladnye i ekrannye datchiki (dlya kontrolya metodom vikhrevykh tokov) / V. S. Sobolev, Yu. M. Shkarlet Novosibirsk: Nauka: 1967. – 144p (in Russian).

11. Abramovych A. O. Rationing of signals of eddy – current converters for correct comparison of them / A. O. Abramovych, V. O. Poddubny // Bulletin of the Ternopil National Technical University. Ser: Technical sciences. –Ternopil. – 2017. – Volume 86 (№2). – P.76-83.

12. Abramovych A. O. Solenoid antenna of radio engineering system of metal identification / A. O. Abramovych, V. O. Piddubnyi // The Journal of Zhytomyr State Technological University” / Engineering. – 2019. – Vol. №1(83). – P. 188-196. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.26642/tn-2019-1\(83\)-188-196](https://doi.org/10.26642/tn-2019-1(83)-188-196)

13. Abramovych A. O. Radio engineering system identification of metals on the basis of eddy-current

converters / A. O. Abramovych, Y. S. Agalidi, V. O. Piddubnyi // Scientific Bulletin of Zaporizhzhya National Technical University, Radioelektronika, Informatics, Management. – 2020. – №1. – P. 7–17. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15588/1607-3274-2020-1-1>

14. Poluprovodnikovaya skhemotekhnika: Spravochnoe rukovodstvo. / U. Tittse, K. Shenk Moskva: Mir: 1982. – 450p (in Russian).

15. Salih M. Fourier Transform – Signal Processing / M. Salih. – Rijeka, Croatia.: InTech, 2012. – 366p. ISBN 978-953-51-0453-7.

16. Ifeachor E. Digital Signal Processing: A Practical Approach 2nd Edition / E. Ifeachor, B. Jervis. – Hoboken, USA.: Prentice Hall, 2001. – 933p. ISBN 978-0201596199

17. Stroustrup B. Programming: principles and practice using C++ (2nd Edition) / Bjarne Stroustrup. – Boston, USA.: Addison-Wesley, 2014. – 2339p.– ISBN 978-0321-992789.

18. Цимбал О.В. Дискримінація металів в металошукачах / О.В. Цимбал//, журнал «Електронна та акустична інженерія» Том. 2 (№4) – 2019. – Київ – С.22-27. URL: <https://doi.org/10.20535/2617-0965.2019.2.4.163837>

19. Abramovych, A., Zaitsev, I., Piddubnyi, V., Bereznychenko, V.: Application of the support vector machines method for metal analyse by an eddy current system. *J. Eng.* 2024, e12346 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1049/tje2.12346>

20. Абрамович А.А., Баженов В.Г., Поддубный В.А. Вихретоковая система идентификации металлических объектов // Sciences of Europe. 2020.